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Calcium Looping (CaL+): Commercialization of a Multiproduct Technology for Decarbonization of CO₂-Intense Industries

Martin Haaf^{a*}, Ari Kettunen^b, Edgardo Coda-Zabetta^b, Mohamed Magdeldin^a

^aSumitomo SHI FW Energia Oy, Metsänneidonkuja 10, 02130 Espoo, Finland

^bSumitomo SHI FW Energia Oy, Relanderinkatu 2, 78200 Varkaus, Finland

Abstract

Carbon capture (CC) as a climate mitigation tool is essential to reach Net-Zero emissions by 2050, according to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). The calcium looping (CaL) process based on circulating fluidized beds (CFB) represents a competitive CC solution to reach CO₂ reduction goals of CO₂-intense industries. CFB-CaL was demonstrated during the 2010s in units of Sumitomo SHI FW's (SFW) design, while focusing on the decarbonization of utilities operating with fossil fuels. SFW is now extending the technology demonstration to new applications, including biomass-based combined heat and power (BioCHP), Waste to Energy (WtE) or Energy from Waste (EfW), Cement and Iron & Steel, targeting the commercial demonstration for 2026-2027. The commercialization of SFW CaL+ is streamlined by exploiting the vast commercial experience in CFB technology proven by a track-record of over 500 CFB boilers delivered based on SFW technology. In this conference contribution we will showcase the specific advantages of the CaL process for decarbonization of CO₂ intense industries, focusing on its application in the WtE/EfW sector.

Keywords: Carbon Capture (CC), Calcium Looping (CaL); Circulating Fluidized Bed (CFB); Waste to Energy (WtE), Energy from Waste (EfW), CFB Oxyfuel combustion; Sumitomo SHI FW (SFW).

Nomenclature

AOD	Argon Oxygen Decarburization
BECCS	Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage
BioCHP	Biomass Combined Heat and Power
CaL	Calcium Looping
CC	Carbon Capture
CDR	Carbon Dioxide Removal
CFB	Circulating Fluidized Bed
EAF	Electric Arc Furnace
EfW	Energy from Waste
FG	Flue Gas
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

* Corresponding author. Email address: martin.haaf@shi-g.com

MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
NET	Negative CO ₂ Emission Technology
WtE	Waste to Energy

1. Introduction

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), carbon capture (CC) is an essential climate mitigation tool to reach Net-Zero emissions by 2050 [1]. The accelerated deployment of CC projects by 2030 is vital in reaching that target. In the first phase of market development, encompassing the period until around 2030, the focus is on capturing CO₂ emissions from existing power plants and industry sectors. Specifically, more than 85% of all CO₂ emissions captured during this decade are anticipated to be captured from plants that have undergone a retrofitting with CO₂ capture equipment. Negative CO₂ emission technologies (NET) or carbon dioxide removal (CDR), i.e. technologies that remove CO₂ from the atmosphere, are required to reach Net-Zero.

The capture and subsequent storage of biogenic CO₂, often referred to as bioenergy with CCS (BECCS), is one option for CDR. In addition to classical biomass fuels, municipal solid waste (MSW) and other waste-derived fuels represent a biogenic carbon containing feedstock for BECCS systems. The global waste generation is directly linked to the growth rate of population and industrial activities and is projected to grow. The spatial distribution of growth projection varies significantly among countries and regions, while the total global waste generation is expected to grow from approximately 2.1 billion tons per year in 2020 up to nearly 4.0 billion tons in 2050 [2]. Irrespective of the implementation of BECCS systems that utilize wastes as feedstock, waste treatment strategies are to be applied to limit the pollution of the ecosystem and the emission of greenhouse gases caused by poor waste treatment strategies such as landfilling or open burning.

The incineration of wastes in Waste-to-Energy (WtE) or Energy from Waste (EfW) represent the dominant waste treatment strategy for non-recyclable fractions within the EU. In 2021, 49 % of total EU MSW was treated via recycling and composting, while waste treatment in WtE plants accounted for 26% of total EU MSW [3]. Hereby, the mass and volume as well as the toxicity of wastes are reduced while as a by-product power and/or heat is generated by utilizing the chemically bound energy in the wastes. WtE plants thus represent a stationary source of biogenic CO₂ in sufficient scale for the implementation of cost-effective BECCS processes. The implementation of Calcium Looping

Figure 1: SFW provides energy, environmental technologies, and services: Global references (over 900 units totaling over 40 GWe of power capacity).

(CaL) represents one option to a) capture CO₂ from WtE plant flue gas (FG) allowing for CDR and thereby turning the WtE plant into a net negative carbon asset, b) maintain and/or increase the waste treatment capacity of the WtE site, and c) potentially improve key techno-economic key performance indicators (KPIs) of the combined system (WtE w/ CaL).

Sumitomo SHI FW (SFW)[†] is a global provider of solutions and services that drive the decarbonization of energy and carbon-intensive industries (Figure 1). SFW's solutions include energy from biomass and waste and integrated CC, along with a host of solutions, such as long duration energy storage, recycling of waste to valuable end products, FG cleaning, waste heat boilers, as well as related services to digitalize, optimize, and decarbonize assets that we deliver to the global power and industrial markets. SFW strives to provide sustainable energy solutions for customers in a wide range of industries including energy, waste, chemicals, metal, sustainable fuels, cement and pulp and paper. SFW's excellence in delivering projects worldwide rely on the company's 1,800 talented people, across 20 locations in 14 countries, with deep know-how and experience in the industry.

2. Calcium Looping - A Multiproduct Carbon Capture Technology

CaL based on circulating fluidized beds (CFB) is a competitive CC solution due to the inherently efficient process combined with its offsetting revenue streams such as additional power and calcined lime. CaL technology can be applied to virtually all carbon-intensive industries, including heat & power, cement plants as well as traditional and future iron- & steelmaking processes. Figure 2 shows the basic principle of the CaL process.

Figure 2: Basic principle of the CaL process.

The core of the process consists of two interconnected CFB reactors, carbonator and calciner. The FG of the upstream industrial process, e.g. a WtE plant, is introduced to the carbonator, where CO₂ is absorbed by solid CaO forming CaCO₃ via exothermic carbonation. The partly carbonated sorbent is subsequently transferred to the calciner. In the calciner, the temperature of the sorbent is raised to allow for endothermic calcination, i.e., sorbent regeneration, and the release of CO₂ to the gas phase, see Eq. (1):

The heat required to run the process is provided via oxy-fuel combustion of additional fuel in the calciner. To maintain the CO₂ carrying capacity of the circulating sorbent, fresh limestone make-up is continuously fed to the process. Consequently, spent sorbent (“purge”) and ash species introduced with the fuel are discharged.

The purge stream consists largely of calcined lime and represents therefore a valuable feedstock for other lime-based processes, e.g., clinker/cement production. The relatively high temperature levels of the core CFB hot loop involving carbonator (~ 650 °C) and calciner (~ 900 °C) allow for an efficient excess heat utilization either via a dedicated water/steam cycle and/or the direct heat utilization involving deep process integration concepts. In essence, the CaL process represents a multi-product technology that provides multiple revenue streams. In addition to the decarbonization of industrial assets, the process supplies additional process heat and/or power as well as calcined lime

[†] <https://www.shi-fw.com/>

which represents a feedstock for clinker/cement manufacturing or other lime-based industries. Moreover, co-capture capabilities of acid gases within the CFB carbonator could potentially replace FG cleaning equipment. The high-temperature process heat from the CaL dual-CFB system is available at different process locations within carbonator and calciner. This allows to partially decouple the heat transfer sections from the sections contaminated by fuel impurities. Moreover, the classical CFB combustion process has proven its dynamic flexibility in commercial installations which makes CFB-CaL also suitable for applications that require a transient flexibility from the CC system. Such requirements are exemplarily known from Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) and Argon Oxygen Decarburization (AOD) processes for the production of iron & steel.

In this article we focus on the application of CaL for WtE/EfW plants. Studies that focus on the application of CaL for other industrial sectors can be found elsewhere [4-6].

3. Calcium Looping for WtE/EfW Plants

Figure 3[‡] shows an example how to retrofit CaL to existing WtE/EfW plants. In this scenario, the plant to be decarbonized consists of two parallel MSW-fired combustion lines. Both lines feed one common steam turbine, delivering heat and/or power to the consumers (Figure 3, a). One combustion line is close to the end of lifetime. As shown in Figure 3 (b) the old line is replaced by a “CaL-line”. The CaL line captures the CO₂ emitted by the remaining MSW combustion line, while delivering a CO₂-product stream for storage and or utilization and a CO₂-depleted FG stream. Furthermore, the high-temperature excess heat available from the CaL island, is utilized to maintain the output of the existing water/steam turbine. The CaL line is fueled by pre-treated MSW and/or industrial wastes. Depending on the specific site conditions, the CaL line may be tailored to fully decarbonize the existing combustion line, while maintaining the total waste treatment capacity of the site (Figure 3, b).

Figure 3: An example of the integration of Calcium Looping for existing WtE/EfW plants (a: Baseline, b: Retrofit).

4. SFW's Roadmap Towards Commercialization of Calcium Looping

SFW is currently performing the CaL technology demonstration for new applications, including Bio-CHP, WtE/EfW, Cement and Iron & Steel to allow for commercial demonstration with partnering customers within 2026 to 2027. A fast commercialization of the CFB-CaL technology is built on the following cornerstones.

[‡] Figure 3 shows an exemplary case involving two grate combustion lines, while the fundamental principle and potential synergy effects, do apply to other cases and/or boundary conditions as well.

4.1. Piloting in TRL 6-8 Demonstration Plants

Pilot-scale testing and demonstration are vital for the development and demonstration of novel technologies. SFW has developed CC solutions since the late 2000s, including the CaL technology based on CFBs, developed jointly with CSIC/HUNOSA/ENDESA over the last 10+ years. The CaL process based on CFBs has been demonstrated already in various pilot plants up to MW-scale, leading to a technology readiness level (TRL) between 6-7, depending on the application scenario in question. The three most relevant existing CFB-CaL pilot plants are listed below:

- 200 kW pilot plant at University of Stuttgart, Germany [7, 8]
- 1.0 MW pilot plant at Technische Universität Darmstadt, Germany, based on SFW technology [9]
- 1.7 MW plant at La Pereda power plant, Spain (Figure 4), based on SFW technology [10, 11]

Figure 4: “La Pereda” 1.7 MW CaL demonstration plant (La Pereda, Spain).

SFW recently joined forces with partnering organizations in the frame of the EU-funded research project HERCCULES to commercialize the CFB-CaL technology for EfW/WtE sector [10]. As part of HERCCULES, SFW is designing, erecting, and commissioning a completely new CaL pilot plant that is tailored for EfW/WtE-specific operation conditions. The pilot plant will be co-located at an existing WtE plant in Milan and will treat (i.e. decarbonize) a slipstream of the WtE plant FG. Importantly, the demonstration scope with the HERCCULES projects includes, in addition to the CO₂ capture via CaL, a CO₂ purification and liquification unit and moreover the transportation and storage of the CO₂ in the Ravenna Hub in the Mediterranean sea. Figure 6 shows the 3D layout of the CaL dual-CFB system, including the following components:

- CFB carbonator reactor, cyclone and loop seal (1-3)
- CFB calciner reactor, cyclone and loop seal (4-6)

Figure 5: “HERCCULES” pilot plant: CaL unit dual-CFB system 3D layout.

In addition to the demonstration activities as part of HERCCULES, SFW is demonstrating the CaL process as part of the CaLby2030 project. Here, the focus is on the demonstration under conditions relevant for Cement, BioCHP and Iron & Steel sectors [8].

4.2. In-House Expertise and Prior Knowledge.

In addition to the extensive test program in the TRL 6-8 pilot plants as listed above, SFW is exploiting its vast in-house expertise, dimensioning tools and databases generated from more than 850 commercial FB combustors and gasifiers, totaling over 40 GW_e of installed power capacity (see Figure 1). CFB boilers for the supply of power and/or heat - commercially operated since 1970 - are perfectly suited to efficiently digest a wide range of fuels, including residue-derived fuels, and different types of biomass or sludges. Intrinsicly, combustion in a hot fluidized bed of solids tolerates fluctuations in fuel quality as typically appearing in the case of waste-derived fuels. CFB systems may be specifically tailored for one single fuel candidate, while multifuel designs are also applied according to the case-specific boundary conditions. In addition to combustion and gasification processes, CFB systems are moreover well suited to efficiently host other gas-solid reactions including carbonation and calcination, as required per the scheme of the CaL process (see Figure 2 and Eq. 1).

Further acceleration in SFW CaL+ technology demonstration is related to similarities in the mode of combustion within the CaL calciner. SFW demonstrated already CFB oxyfuel combustion in 30 MW_{th} scale during the 2010s at the Fundacion Ciudad de la Energia (CIUDEN, Spain), accumulating thousands of operational hours under various conditions. Based on the demonstration activities, commercial development with partners led to the completion of FEED activities and development of a readily available 300 MWe CFB Oxyfuel power plant design [12]. Now, those experiences allow us to upscale more rapidly the SFW CaL+ technology, since in both processes (CFB-CaL calciner, and CFB oxyfuel boiler) the fuel is combusted in a CFB oxyfuel environment.

5. Summary and Conclusion

The implementation of CC technologies as a climate mitigation tool is required to reach Net-Zero emissions by 2050. The accelerated deployment of CC projects by 2030, is essential in reaching that target. Sumitomo SHI FW (SFW) - as a technology forerunner - is currently expanding the SFW CaL+ technology demonstration to new applications, including Bio-CHP, WtE, cement and iron & steel. Such demonstration is due in relevant industrial environments, targeting commercial readiness in 2026-2027, depending on the application.

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